

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF SUPER HIGH EFFICIENCY THREE JUNCTION SERIES CONNECTED TANDEM SOLAR CELL

Md Abul Hossion¹, Abu Kowsar ¹, Chandan Kumar Howlader² Zahid Hasan Mahmood¹
1. Department of Applied Physics Electronics & Communication Engineering, University of
Dhaka 1205, Bangladesh
2. Department of Electrical & Electronic Engineering, Eastern University, Dhaka 1207,
Bangladesh
Email: jonyphys@yahoo.com

Abstract: Theoretical efficiency has been calculated for three-junction series connected solar cell using air mass 1.5 global. This efficiency depends on the band gap. If a high band gap is chosen to obtain a high voltage cell, the current is low because most of the solar spectrum is sub-band-gap light, and, therefore, is not absorbed. If the band gap is decreased so that most of the spectrum is absorbed, then the voltage of the cell is decreased. Here we use a high band gap material GaInP₂ as top cell parameter whose thickness is very thin. And a low band gap material GaAs as middle cell parameter whose thickness is more than that of top cell thickness. A much lower band gap material Ge as bottom cell parameter whose thickness is more than that of middle cell thickness. To produce optical transparency and maximum current conductivity between top and bottom cells these three materials are lattice matched. So electrons can easily pass through the junctions. Using mathematical formulation and studying properties of GaInP₂ and GaAs and Ge the theoretical efficiencies for three junction solar cells fabricated with these materials would be explained on analysis. Future prospects for realizing super-high-efficiency and low-cost tandem solar cells are also discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION

Here we report the theoretical efficiency of a series connected, triple junction tandem solar cell with optimized cell thicknesses. The primary increase in efficiency results from an increased in current as the top-cell thickness is optimized. For ideal cell (i.e., cells with low surface recombination velocities) the thinner top cells also lead to increased open circuit voltages, resulting in even greater improvements in the efficiencies.

2. METHODOLOGY

The theoretical solar cell efficiencies were calculated for air-mass AM1.5G at 298K temperature, using the total power density is 1000 w/m² [1]. The calculation assumed zero losses from reflection and series resistance. We calculated the short circuit current J_{sc} [2]. Where

$$J_{sc} = e \times F \quad (1)$$

$$F = \frac{\lambda I}{hc} \quad (2)$$

The reverse saturation current density J₀ [1] is calculated from the values given in Table 3 and Table 3. The intrinsic carrier concentration n_i were calculated from [3]

$$n_i^2 = N_c N_v \exp\left(\frac{-E_g}{kT}\right) \quad (3)$$

$$N_c N_v = 4M_c M_v \left(\frac{2\pi kT}{h^2}\right)^3 (m_e^* m_h^*)^{\frac{3}{2}} \quad (4)$$

A cell with band gap E_g when exposed to solar spectrum a photon with energy greater than E_g contributes an energy E_g to the cell output & the excess over E_g is wasted as heat. The total current could be estimated using the following equation [4]

$$I = J_0 \left(e^{\frac{qV}{kT}} - 1 \right) - J_{sc} \quad (5)$$

Where potential barrier is

$$V = 0.0259 \ln \left(\frac{N_a \times N_d}{n_i^2} \right) \quad (6)$$

Open circuit voltage V_{oc} can be calculated from this equation, i.e. I = 0,

$$V_{oc} = \left(\frac{kT}{e} \right) \ln \left[\left(\frac{J_{sc}}{J_0} \right) + 1 \right] \quad (7)$$

For conversion efficiency of solar cell we use [4],

$$\eta = \frac{V_{oc} \times J_{sc} \times F.F.}{P_{in}} \times 100\% \quad (8)$$

We can calculate the efficiency of each cell (Top, Middle, and Bottom) using equation (8) in the same way efficiency of the triple junction series connected tandem cell GaInP/GaAs/Ge.

3. CALCULATION & SIMULATION

TABLE 1. Value obtained by computer simulation

Material	J_{sc} Amp	J_m Amp	V_{oc} Volt	V_m Volt	F.F %	Eff. %	E_g eV
GaInP	463.62	442.54	0.65	0.57	0.83	Not estimated	1.82
GaAs	566.65	517.65	0.40	0.30	0.74		1.42
Ge	772.71	653.51	0.23	0.17	0.63		0.66
Combination of GaInP, GaAs and Ge	463.62	442.54	1.28	1.04	0.78	46	—

TABLE 2: Efficiency calculation for different air mass

Radiation data for air mass	Radiation Input W/m^2	Efficiency of GaInP (B)	Efficiency of GaAs (C)	Efficiency of Ge (D)	Efficiency of GaInP/GaAs/Ge (E)
AM0	1367	23	12	9	42
AM1	1100	19	13	9	36
AM1.5D	850	22	16	8	34
AM1.5G	1000	25	15	11	46
AM2	750	22	15	4	21

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For lower surface velocities, the V_{oc} increases as the n layer is thinned down. However, it should be noted that the V_{oc} is expected to decrease as the cell is thinned when the surface-recombination velocity is high. The same is equally applicable to p-type material if all subscripts are replaced appropriately. The optimal top-cell thickness would be achieved for the current-matched condition at the maximum-power point, rather than under short-circuit conditions as we

have calculated. Reduction of the thickness of top-cell results an increase in the efficiencies for a range of band-gap combination.

The effect of the properties of the material's shown in Table: 3 are considered. In order to apply super-high-efficiency cells widely, it is necessary to improve their conversion efficiency and reduced their cost. Efficiency can be increased in top cell, middle cell, and bottom cell, by using materials of different band gap as shown in graph (Fig:1.a,b and c).

Fig. a

Fig. b

Figure 1: (a) Top cell band gap Versace efficiency (b) Middle cell band gap Versace efficiency (c) Bottom cell band gap Versace efficiency (d) Top cell thickness Versace total cell efficiency are graphically shown.

TABLE 3. Parameters of the materials for Solar cell [3]

Parameter	Top Cell GaInP	Middle Cell GaAs	Bottom Cell Ge
N_A	10^{17} cm^3	10^{17} cm^3	$1.04 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^3$
N_D	$2 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^3$	$2 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^3$	$6 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^3$
E_g	1.82eV	1.42eV	0.66eV
Lattice constant	5.65	5.65	5.65

TABLE 4. Considered value for the thickness of different cell

Parameter	Top Cell GaInP	Middle Cell GaAs	Bottom Cell Ge
x_n	$150 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}$	$300 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}$	$300 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}$
x_p	$400 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}$	$4000 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}$	$4000 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}$

The efficiency can be calculated from chosen band gap of different materials. The graphs are shown here will be useful in choosing which materials to be studied. Again efficiency increases as we decrease the thickness of the top cell which is shown in Fig:1 (d). Thus the total cell efficiency is also increased. Our calculated efficiency was 46 % under one sun. Effect of optimize thickness on efficiency also shown graphically. Temperature is related to the efficiency as temperature increases, excess heat cause a decrease in efficiency. Efficiency can be achieved more than 50% optimizing the top cell thickness. In practical cases inter connection between cells and layers produce series resistance, reflection from the top surface reduces irradiance, variation in air mass, absorption of radiation by different layers producing heat, also

effect the efficiency of the multi junction solar cell. In this paper efficiency variation with the change in air mass is shown in table 2, which is also shown graphically in fig: 2. From Fig 2, efficiency is calculated for single cell GaInP, GaAs, Ge, and also for combination of GaInP/GaAs/Ge triple junction series connected tandem solar cell. Efficiency of triple junction series connected solar cell is more than 40 % in air mass 1.5G under one sun. In other cases a decrease in efficiency is observed. In case of AM0 in spite of having more irradiance the efficiency does not increase in that way it may be due to extra photon's energy losses as heat. This triple junction solar cell is shown to be good for terrestrial use. Future research can be done with concentrated sun light with reducing the extra heat by applying cooling techniques.

Figure 2: Variation of efficiency of different solar cell due to change in air mass. Curve D shows efficiency of bottom cell Ge in different air mass. Curve C shows efficiency of middle cell GaAs in different air mass. Curve B shows efficiency of top cell GaInP in different air mass. Curve E shows efficiency of combination of GaInP/GaAs/Ge cell Ge in different air mass.

5. CONCLUSION

We have calculated the theoretical efficiencies of three-junction, series-connected tandem solar cell with the thicknesses of the top cell optimized to achieve current matching. Thinning down the top-cell thickness in some cases resulted in large increases in the calculated efficiencies. Most of the increase came from the higher J_{sc} achieved by current matching. In the case of low surface recombination velocities the V_{oc} also increased when the top-cell was thinned. Reduction of top-cell thickness results in significant increases in the efficiencies for a range of band-gap combination. The primary increase in efficiency results from an increased current as the top-cell thickness is optimized. For ideal cell (i.e., cells with low surface recombination velocities) the thinner top cells also lead to increased open circuit voltages, resulting in even greater improvements in the efficiencies.

6. REFERENCE

- [1] M. A. Green, Keith Emery, Yoshihiro Hishikawa, Wilhelm Warta. Solar cell efficiency tables (version 33). Progress in photovoltaics: research and application 17: 85-94, 2009.
- [2] M. E. Ne11 and A. M. Barnett, IEEE Transaction on electron devices, Vol. 34, No 2, 1987.
- [3] S.R.Kurtz, P.Faine, and J.M.Olison ,J.Appl. Phys. Vol.68, No 4, 1990.
- [4] S. M. Sze, Physics of Semiconductor Devices, 2nd ed. Wiley, New York, 1981.